

Investigating the Levels of SMEs' Participation in International Trade in Zambia: A Case Study of SMEs in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center

Nosiku Mwanza¹ & Peter Silwimba^{2*}

¹*School of Humanities and Business, Information and Communications University, Lusaka, Zambia*

²*Risk Department National Savings and Credit Bank, Lusaka, Zambia*

**School of Humanities and Business, Information and Communications University, Lusaka, Zambia*

*Corresponding Author: Peter Silwimba, Email silwimbap47@gmail.com

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 13th Dec 2025</p> <p>Keywords: International trade Small and Medium Enterprises Kamwala Trading Center Zambia</p>	<p>Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are a crucial component of Zambia's economy, representing approximately 90% of all businesses and providing livelihoods for about 80% of the workforce. Despite their significance, SMEs in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center remain underrepresented in international trade, highlighting a need to understand the factors influencing their participation and the challenges they face. The purpose of this study was to examine the levels of Zambia's SMEs' participation in international trade. A mixed-methods approach was employed, with 50 SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center, and data analysis was performed using Megastat. The results show that product quality and standards (50%) and understanding buyer preferences (58%) are key factors influencing international trade participation. The chi-square test results indicate that there is no significant association between the type of business and the main factor influencing the ability to engage in international trade ($\chi^2 = 12.05$, $p = 0.7404$), indicating that factors influencing international trade engagement are similar across different types of businesses, including retail, wholesale, manufacturing, services, and others. However, 76% of SMEs are unaware of support programs. The study further reveals that high transportation costs (42%), currency exchange rate risks (38%), and delays at borders/customs (20%) are major challenges faced by SMEs when engaging in international trade. The ANOVA test reveals that there is no significant relationship between the independent variables (type of business and years of operation) and the dependent variable (biggest challenge faced by SMEs in international trade), with an F-value of 0.48 and a p-value of 0.6247, indicating that the model is not a good fit for the data, suggesting that other factors not included in the model may be more important in determining the biggest challenge faced by SMEs in international trade. The study concludes that SMEs face significant challenges in international trade, but opportunities exist through digital methods (social media, 52%) affordable finance (42%) and partnerships with foreign buyers/distributors (38%). The study recommends implementing capacity building, improving access to finance, enhancing digital literacy, encouraging partnerships, and increasing awareness of support programs.</p>

1. Introduction

1.1 Background of the study

Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) constitute as a backbone of Zambia's economy, making substantial contributions to employment generation and GDP growth while serving as vital drivers of economic development. According to recent data from the Zambia Development Agency, SMEs represent approximately 90% of all businesses in the country and provide livelihoods for about 80% of the workforce Zambia (ZDA 2022). Despite their dominant position in the domestic economy, Zambia's SMEs participate minimally in international trade compared to larger corporations, with formal exports being predominantly dominated by mining and large-scale agricultural enterprises (Kolala & Dokowe 2021).

This disparity is particularly evident in Lusaka's bustling trading centers like Kamwala, where thousands of SMEs engage in vibrant wholesale and retail activities but rarely expand beyond informal cross-border trade with neighboring countries (Kapapa 2023). According to Chola (2021), multiple interconnected challenges hinder SMEs in Lusaka from participating effectively in international trade, with financial constraints representing the most formidable barrier. While Mwansa and Mwanza (2023)

pointed out that, most of small businesses struggle to access the capital required for international trade requirements such as product certification, quality packaging, and bulk production, as commercial banks typically view them as high-risk clients demanding stringent collateral and offering unfavorable interest rates.

However, there are promising enablers that enhance the international competitiveness of Lusaka's SME sector, including regional trade agreements like COMESA and the Africa Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), digital transformation, government support programs, and the natural clustering of SMEs in hubs like Kamwala Trading Center (Kyereboah-Coleman, 2025). These enablers suggest that with targeted policy interventions and support mechanisms, trading center SMEs could transform into meaningful players in regional and international markets (Ajibo, 2024).

The limited but growing participation of Lusaka's SMEs in international trade represents a significant untapped opportunity for Zambia's economic diversification and development. While substantial barriers persist across financial, regulatory, informational, and infrastructural domains, the identified enablers suggest that with targeted policy interventions and support mechanisms, trading center SMEs could transform into meaningful players in regional and global markets (Mwansa, 2024; UNCTAD 2021). Successful SME internationalization would yield multiplier effects including job creation, technology transfer, and overall business ecosystem enhancement.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Many Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) operating in Lusaka's busy trading centers, including Kamwala, continue to face significant obstacles that prevent them from participating in international markets, despite the substantial potential benefits of international trade for economic growth and business expansion (Kapapa 2023). According to Hailu and Tshehla (2024), traditional banks frequently impose strict collateral requirements and high interest rates that are prohibitive for small-scale traders, making it difficult for them to obtain affordable financing options. A significant knowledge gap that deters export attempts is also caused by the fact that many SME owners struggle with a lack of understanding of complicated export procedures, international trade laws, and foreign market requirements (Baker and Le 2024). SMEs find it challenging to maintain the consistent quality and prompt delivery necessary for international trade due to logistical constraints like inadequate storage facilities, unreliable electricity supply, and poor transportation infrastructure (Musonda 2024). Furthermore, a lot of business owners are unaware of regional trade agreements and government assistance programs that could make it easier for them to enter international markets. Additional obstacles to global market penetration include the lack of well-established networks with foreign buyers and the inability to fulfill large-volume orders (Lemma 2024). This study specifically aims to fill the critical knowledge gap regarding why SMEs in Lusaka's trading centers continue to be significantly underrepresented in formal international trade activities, despite their substantial contribution to the local economy.

1.3.1 General Objective

To examine the levels of SMEs' participation in international trade in Zambia, with a focus on Lusaka's Kamwala trading center.

1.3.2 Specific Objectives

- To identify the factors that influence SMEs' participation in international trade in Lusaka's Kamwala trading center.
- To assess the challenges faced by SMEs in Lusaka's Kamwala trading center when engaging in international trade.
- To explore the opportunities available for SMEs to enhance their involvement in global markets at Lusaka's Kamwala trading center.

1.4 Research Questions

- What factors influence SMEs' participation in international trade in Lusaka's Kamwala trading center?
- What are the main challenges hindering SMEs from engaging in international trade at Lusaka's Kamwala trading center?
- What opportunities exist for SMEs to increase their participation in global markets at Lusaka's Kamwala trading center?

1.5 The Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework outlines the key dimensions influencing SME participation in international trade at Kamwala Trading Center, directly addressing the research question about factors affecting their global market engagement. The framework organizes these factors into three core categories: internal firm-level characteristics, external environmental conditions, and contemporary enablers. Internal factors include export knowledge, product quality, and management capacity, which determine an SME's readiness to compete internationally. External factors encompass infrastructure limitations, institutional support systems, and trade regulations that create the business environment. Modernity factors highlight current opportunities through trade agreements and technology adoption that could help overcome traditional barriers.

Independent Variables

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

1.6 The Significant of this Study

This study is significant as it addressed the critical gap in understanding the factors influenced SME participation in international trade in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center. The findings provided evidence-based insights for policymakers to design targeted interventions, such as streamlined export procedures and financial support mechanisms, to enhance SME competitiveness in global markets. The research offered practical guidance for SME owners and entrepreneurs on overcoming challenges related to export readiness, market access, and logistical constraints. It also contributed to the broader discourse on SME internationalization in developing economies, enriching theoretical frameworks on SME globalization and providing a foundation for future studies. Ultimately, the study aligned with Zambia's economic diversification goals, advocating for SME-led trade as a driver of sustainable development.

2. Literature Review**2.1 Factors Influencing SME Participation in International Trade**

Access to finance remains one of the most significant determinants of SME participation in international trade (Lemma 2024). The capital requirements for engaging in cross-border trade often exceed the financial capacity of most small enterprises, creating a substantial barrier to market entry (Nuwagaba 2015). Mwansa and Mwanza (2023) noted that Traditional financial institutions like commercial banks typically perceive SMEs as high-risk clients due to their limited collateral and unpredictable cash flows, resulting in stringent lending conditions. Chisala (2008) found that Many Kamwala-based traders report difficulties securing trade finance instruments such as letters of credit or export credit guarantees, which are essential for managing payment risks in international transactions.

Nave and Ferreira (2024) observed that high interest rates attached to the few available loan products further erode the already thin profit margins characteristic of small-scale trading businesses. Koreen and Cusmano (2019) found that alternative financing options like microfinance institutions often have insufficient capital bases to meet the needs of import/export operations, while informal lending systems carry prohibitive costs. This financing gap forces many otherwise viable SMEs to either abandon international trade aspirations or resort to informal cross-border trading channels with higher risks (Musonda 2024) According to Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry (2022) in Zambia, the situation is exacerbated by limited awareness of existing government-backed financing programs like those offered through the Citizens Economic Empowerment Commission.

Kalima,(2023) Even when financing is secured, the short repayment periods typically demanded by lenders often misalign with the longer cash conversion cycles inherent in international trade. Without systemic solutions to improve access to affordable, trade-specific financing, many Kamwala SMEs will remain confined to domestic markets despite their export potential. The regulatory environment surrounding international trade presents a complex web of challenges for SMEs Trading seeking to expand beyond domestic borders. Lwesya (2021) found that many SME owners lack the specialized knowledge required to complete the extensive documentation for exports, including certificates of origin, phytosanitary certificates for agricultural products, and conformity assessment reports.

Malecka (2017) alluded that frequent changes in trade policies and inconsistent enforcement of regulations add another layer of uncertainty, discouraging SMEs from making long-term investments in export capabilities. At border posts, small traders often

face demands for unofficial payments that inflate the cost of doing business across borders. The complexity increases when dealing with varying import regulations across different destination markets, particularly for processed goods subject to technical barriers to trade

The level of entrepreneurial skills and trade-specific knowledge among SME owners is significantly influencing their capacity to engage successfully in international markets. Chola (2021) stated that many traders possess strong domestic business acumen but lack specialized competencies required for cross-border operations, such as understanding incoterms, managing foreign exchange risks, or navigating international payment systems. Knowledge gaps about export procedures often lead to costly mistakes in documentation or failure to meet destination market requirements, resulting in rejected shipments and financial losses (Kolala & Dokowe 2021). Most SME owners have limited understanding of regional trade agreements like COMESA or the AfCFTA that could provide preferential market access, missing opportunities to reduce tariff burdens (Hailu & Tshehla 2024).

2.2 Challenges Faced by SMEs in International Trade

Export expenses extend far beyond simple product costs, encompassing a complex web of logistical, regulatory, and transactional expenditures that collectively create substantial barriers to entry (Malecka 2017). Shipping and freight charges often consume disproportionate percentages of SMEs' profit margins, particularly for smaller consignments that cannot benefit from economies of scale. Customs duties and tariffs, while sometimes reduced under regional trade agreements, still impose heavy financial burdens when combined with various export license fees and inspection costs (Naradda et al. 2020). SMEs struggle with the hidden expenses of international trade compliance, including product testing and certification fees required by destination markets (Lwesya 2021)

Kapapa (2023) found that most of the small traders lack systematic mechanisms for gathering intelligence about foreign demand patterns, competitor analysis, or price trends in potential export markets. This information asymmetry creates substantial risks when attempting to enter new markets, often leading to costly missteps in product adaptation or pricing strategies (Alex & Taotais 2021). Language barriers compound this challenge, limiting access to market reports and trade opportunities published in foreign language (Alex & Taotais 2021). This knowledge gap extends to limited understanding of distribution channels, buyer preferences, and marketing strategies that differ significantly from domestic operations (Mwape 2021).

Kafwabalula and Mwange (2025) physical infrastructure limitations in Zambia create substantial operational challenges for Kamwala's SMEs attempting to engage in international trade. Poor road conditions lead to frequent delays, product damage, and increased vehicle maintenance costs that disproportionately affect small-scale traders (Du 2020). At border crossings, inefficient customs processing infrastructure creates bottlenecks that are particularly damaging to time-sensitive SME shipments (Rodrik 2018). Sibangilizwe and Jeffrey (2019) pointed out that currency fluctuation risks present additional financial management challenges for businesses without hedging capabilities or foreign exchange expertise. exposed to shipment risks.

2.3 Opportunities exist for SMEs to Increase their Participation in Global Markets

To overcome these obstacles, SMEs must leverage key opportunities such as regional trade agreements, digital trade platforms, and government support programs (Zambia Development Agency 2022). According to AfCFTA (2023) One of the most significant opportunities for SME growth in global markets is the increasing number of regional trade agreements (RTAs), which reduce trade barriers and create more accessible markets for small businesses. Agreements such as the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) have been instrumental in promoting intra-regional trade by eliminating tariffs and simplifying customs procedures. For SMEs, this means lower costs when exporting goods and services to neighboring countries, making them more competitive against larger corporations.

Another major driver of SME globalization is the rise of digital platforms for trade, which have revolutionized how small businesses connect with international buyers and suppliers. E-commerce platforms like Alibaba, Amazon, and eBay allow SMEs to reach global consumers without the need for a physical presence in foreign markets (International Trade Centre 2022). Social media and digital advertising also play a crucial role in brand building, allowing SMEs to compete with larger firms on a more level playing field. As digital infrastructure continues to improve worldwide, SMEs that embrace these platforms will have a distinct advantage in scaling their operations globally (UNCTAD 2021).

Government support programs are another critical factor in facilitating SME expansion into global markets. Many governments offer grants, subsidies, and low-interest loans to help SMEs overcome financial constraints when entering international trade. Export promotion agencies provide training, market research, and networking opportunities to assist SMEs in identifying viable export markets (Ministry of Commerce, Trade and Industry 2022).

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Designs

The study employed a mixed-methods design. This research design is deemed to be suitable for this investigation because it enables to investigate the levels of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) participation in international trade in Zambia, focusing specifically on SMEs operating in Kamwala Trading Center, Lusaka. Furthermore, this design enabled the assessment of statistical relationships among the variables such as household size, consumption, savings and investment.

3.2 Target Population

The target population for this study were small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) operating within Kamwala Trading Center, Zambia, that are currently engaged in or possess potential for cross-border trade activities.

3.3 Sampling Design

The study utilized stratified random technique to ensure that comprehensive representation of SMEs across Kamwala Trading Center. The sampling strategy incorporates four key stratification criteria; geographical location, business sector, enterprise size and trade engagement level. Therefore, this technique supported study’s objectives.

3.4 Sampling Size Determination

The sample size of 50 SMEs was used during data collection form Kamwala Trading Center.

3.5 Data Collection Methods

This study collected primary data for analysis. Structured questionnaires were administered to systematically collect quantitative data from a representative sample of SMEs, focusing on measurable aspects such as financial constraints, regulatory challenges, and digital trade adoption from SMEs operating within Kamwala Trading Center.

3.6 Data Analysis

The study used Megastat to analyse the data, which were coded, cleaned and analysed through descriptive statistics to summarize the demographic characteristics of respondent SMEs and their key challenges in global market participation. Subsequently, inferential statistical techniques were applied, including regression analysis to identify significant predictors of export success and chi-square tests to examine association between categorical variables.

4 Findings

4.1 Background Characteristics

4.1.1 Current Position in the Business

As shown in figure 1 below, the data reveals a relatively even distribution of respondents across various positions within their businesses. Managers make up the largest group, accounting for 30% (15 respondents), followed closely by Employees at 28% (14 respondents), and Owners at 26% (13 respondents). The remaining 16% (8 respondents) identify as partners or hold other positions. This suggests that the survey captured a diverse range of perspectives from different levels of the business hierarchy, providing a well-rounded view of SME participation in international trade in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center.

Figure 2: Current Position in Business

4.1.2 Type of Business

The respondents were asked to state their type of business as shown in figure 2 below, the data shows that the 42% of respondents were engaged in retail trade, followed by wholesale businesses with 36%. This indicates that trading activities, including both retail and wholesale, dominate the business landscape, accounting for 78% of the respondents. Manufacturing and services sectors are underrepresented, with only 2% respondent each. While 18% indicated Other categories, suggesting some diversification beyond the primary retail and wholesale activities.

Figure 3 Type of Business

4.1.3 Business Owner

The respondents were engaged to state if they were the owner of the business as shown in figure 3 below. The findings shows that the majority of respondents (74%) were not owners of the business, while 26% identified as owners. This suggests that the survey captured a larger proportion of non-owner perspectives, potentially including managers, employees, and other stakeholders, providing a broader view of SME participation in international trade in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center.

Figure 4: Business Owner

4.1.4 Years of Operation in this Business

The respondents were asked to state how long they have been in the business, the data in figure 4 below, reveals that 52% of respondents their business has been in operational for more than 10 years, indicating a high level of experience and stability among the surveyed SMEs. Additionally, 32% (16 businesses) has been in operational for 7-10 years, suggesting a significant proportion of established businesses. The data also shows that 12% (6 businesses) have operated for 4-6 years, while only 2% (1 business each) have operated for less than 1 year and 1-3 years, respectively. This suggests that the surveyed SMEs were generally well-established and have a strong presence in the market.

Figure 5 Years of Operation in this Business

4.1.5 Number of Employees in your Business

As shown in figure 5 below, the data shows that the 66% of respondents employed between 1-5 workers, indicating that most SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center are micro or small enterprises. Additionally, 16% employ 6-10 workers, while 10% employ 11-20 workers. Only 8% employ over 20 workers, suggesting that medium-sized enterprises are relatively scarce in the surveyed population. This distribution highlights the prevalence of small-scale businesses in the trading center.

Figure 6 Number of Employees in your Business

4.2 Factors that Influence SMEs Participation in International Trade in Lusaka Kamwala Trading Center.

4.2.1 Does your business currently engage in international trade (export or import)

The respondents were asked to state they do participate in international trade, as shown in figure 6 below. The data indicates that all respondents (100%, 50 businesses) are currently engaged in international trade, either through export or import activities. This suggests that the surveyed SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center are actively participating in global markets, highlighting the importance of international trade to their business operations.

Figure 7 Engage in Trade

4.2.2 Approximately Percentage of Total Sales/Revenue from International Trade

The respondents were asked to state if they have been engaged in international trade and approximately what percentage of total sales or revenue raised from international trade. As shown in figure 7 below, all the surveyed businesses engage in international trade, with varying degrees of reliance on it. A combined 66% derive more than half their revenue from international trade, showing it's a major contributor for most. Specifically, 34% get 51-75% of sales from international trade, and 32% depend on it for over 75% of revenue. Only 4% have minimal international sales (under 10%). This underscores how vital global markets are to these SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center.

Figure 8: Revenue from International Trade

4.2.3 Average Monthly Value of Exports or Imports

As shown in figure 8 below, the findings reveals that nearly half (46%) of the SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center had an average monthly export/import value between ZMW 50,001 and ZMW 100,000, indicating a moderate scale of international trade. A significant proportion of 26% trade between ZMW 20,001 and ZMW 50,000, while 18% (9 businesses) exceed ZMW 100,000, suggesting substantial international trade involvement. Only a small fraction of 2% reported values below ZMW 5,000. The majority (88%) of SMEs fall within the ZMW 20,001 to ZMW 100,000 range, highlighting a concentration of moderate-scale international traders in the surveyed population.

Figure 9 Monthly Value of Exports or Imports

4.2.4 Main Factor Influencing Your Ability to Engage in International Trade

The respondents in this study expressed diverse factors influencing their ability to engage in international trade, as shown in figure 9 below. The findings indicate that product quality and standards are the main factors influencing SMEs' ability to engage in international trade, with 50% of respondents citing this as a key challenge. This suggests that meeting international quality standards is a crucial aspect of SMEs' participation in global markets. Knowledge of foreign markets (18%) and access to finance (22%) are also significant factors, although to a lesser extent. Trade regulations (8%) and no major influence (2%) are less prominent factors. These findings highlight the importance of product quality and standards in facilitating SMEs' engagement in international trade, and suggest that efforts to improve quality standards could have a positive impact on SMEs' participation in global markets.

Figure 10 Factors Influencing International Trade

4.2.5 The Most Difficult Aspect of International Trade for Your Business

The responses in Figure 10 below reveals that the biggest challenge SMEs face in international trade is understanding buyer preferences, cited by 58% (29 businesses) of respondents. This highlights the importance of market research and understanding customer needs. Export documentation and procedures are a challenge for 24% (12 businesses), while identifying international customers is a hurdle for 18% (9 businesses). Notably, no respondents reported meeting packaging and product standards as a difficulty, possibly indicating they've already overcome this hurdle or it's not a major concern.

Figure 11 Challenges of International Trade

4.2.7 The Chi-Square Test – Business Types and Factors Influencing Ability to Engage in International Trade.

The chi-square test in table 1 results below indicates that there is no significant association between the type of business and the main factor influencing the ability to engage in international trade ($\chi^2 = 12.05$, $df = 16$, $p = 0.7404$). This suggests that the factors influencing international trade engagement are similar across different types of businesses, including retail, wholesale, manufacturing, services, and others. The p-value of 0.7404 is greater than the typical significance level of 0.05, indicating that the observed differences in the main factors influencing international trade engagement across different types of businesses can be

attributed to chance rather than any underlying relationship. Therefore, it can be concluded that the type of business does not have a significant impact on the main factor influencing SMEs' ability to engage in international trade.

Table 1 A Chi-square Test of Significance

Type of business	Which of the following is the main factor influencing your ability to engage in international trade					Total
	Access to finance	Knowledge of foreign markets	Trade regulations	Product quality/standards	No major influence	
Retail	4	4	1	11	1	21
Manufacturing	1	0	0	0	0	1
Wholesale	3	4	1	10	0	18
Services	1	0	0	0	0	1
Other	2	1	2	4	0	9
Total	11	9	4	25	1	50
12.05 chi-square 16 df .7404 p-value						

4.3 Objective 2: The Challenges Faced by SMEs in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center when Engaging in International Trade

4.3.1 The Most Challenges Affecting Your Business in International Trade

Figure 12 below, highlights the major challenges most of the business encountered, among the challenges high transportation costs emerge to be the most challenge for SMEs in international trade, affecting 42% (21 businesses) of respondents. Currency exchange rate risks were also significant, impacting 38% (19 businesses) of SMEs, likely due to fluctuations affecting pricing and profitability. While 20% (10 businesses) of respondents indicated that delays at borders/customs were also the challenge faced, potentially disrupting supply chains. However, no respondents cited limited connections with foreign buyers or regulatory compliance issues, suggesting these were not major concerns, possibly due to established networks or manageable regulatory frameworks.

Figure 12 Challenges Faced in Trade

4.3.2 Biggest challenge your business currently faces in international trade

When respondents were asked to state what was biggest challenge for their businesses encountered in international trade. The study findings in figure 13 below shows that Access to financing was the biggest challenge SMEs face in international trade, cited by 44% (22 businesses) of respondents. Customs procedures were also a significant hurdle, affecting 30% (15 businesses) of SMEs, likely due to bureaucratic delays or complexities. Competition from large firms is a challenge for 26% (13 businesses), indicating smaller businesses struggle to compete with bigger players. Notably, no respondents reported meeting international standards or market access as challenges, suggesting these are either well-managed or not pressing concerns for these businesses.

Figure 13 Major Challenges

4.4 Explore the Opportunities Available for SMEs to Enhance their Involvement in Global Markets at Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center.

4.4.1 Have you heard of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA)

The respondents were asked if they have heard of African continental free trade area (AfCFTA). The results in figure 13 shows that 84% (42 businesses) of Zambian SMEs have heard of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA), indicating a high level of awareness about this landmark agreement. Only 16% (8 businesses) are unaware, suggesting that efforts to promote AfCFTA has been effective in reaching the business community, and SMEs are likely poised to leverage its benefits.

Figure 15 Awareness

4.4.2 The Digital Method used to reach international customers

The respondents were engaged to find out the digital method used to reach out to international customers. The findings in figure 14 below shows that Over half (52%) of Zambian SMEs primarily use social media to reach international customers, highlighting its importance in accessing global markets. Followed by E-commerce platforms used by 30% (15 businesses) of respondents. A small portion (4%, 2 businesses) were not using any digital methods, while 14% (7 businesses) rely on other approaches, indicating a reliance on diverse strategies to connect with international customers.

Figure 16 Digital Methods In Trade

4.4.3 Opportunities that the Business May be Interested in to Enhance International Trade

When respondents were inquired about opportunities that their business would be interested to be interested in to enhance the international trade. The results as shown in figure 16 reveals that the top opportunity for enhancing international trade is partnering with foreign buyers/distributors, cited by 38% (19 businesses) of respondents. Receiving export funding or grants is also highly sought after, with 34% (17 businesses) expressing interest. Government export training and promotion programs appeal to 16% (8 businesses), while joining SME export cooperatives is of interest to 12% (6 businesses). Notably, no respondents indicated disinterest, highlighting the eagerness of Zambian SMEs to explore opportunities and grow their international trade footprint.

Figure 17 Enhancing Trade Participation

4.4.4 Form of Support Required to Boost Business Growth in International Trade

The respondents were asked to indicate what form of support would be required to boost their businesses in international trade. The findings in figure 16 below disclose that 42% (21 businesses) of respondents stated that affordable finance would make the biggest difference for Zambian SMEs' growth in international trade. Follow by those who indicated that better infrastructure, such as roads and internet, is also crucial, with 22% (11 businesses) highlighting its importance. While 16% of respondents stated that offering export training and skills would increase the growth in international trade, and 12% of the respondents indicated simplified regulations were also important for accelerating growth in international trade, while only 8% of respondents seen marketing and trade promotion as less critical, indicating SMEs prioritize foundational support to access and succeed in international markets.

Figure 18 Form of Support in Trade

4.4.5 The regression analysis test

The regression analysis shows that the model is not a good fit for the data, with an R-squared value of 0.008, indicating that only 0.8% of the variation in the number of international customers or partners is explained by the independent variables. The ANOVA table confirms that the model is not statistically significant, with an F-value of 0.18 and a p-value of 0.8330. This suggests that the independent variables (awareness of AfCFTA and digital method used to reach international customers) do not have a significant impact on the number of international customers or partners. The correlation coefficient (R) is 0.088, indicating a very weak positive correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The p-values for both independent variables are greater than 0.05, indicating that neither awareness of AfCFTA nor digital method used to reach international customers has a statistically significant relationship with the number of international customers or partners. Overall, the results suggest that the model is not effective in explaining the number of international customers or partners, and other factors may be more important in determining this outcome.

Table 3: Statistical Significant Test

Regression Analysis						
	R ²	0.008		n	50	
	Adjusted R ²	0.000		k	2	
	R	0.088		Dep. Var.	How many international customers or partners has your business engaged with in the past 12 months	
	Std. Error	1.018				
ANOVA table						
Source	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	
Regression	0.3805	2	0.1903	0.18	.8330	
Residual	48.7395	47	1.0370			
Total	49.1200	49				
Regression output						
variables	coefficients	std. error	t (df=47)	p-value	confidence interval	
Intercept	4.2025	0.6207	6.770	1.82E-08	2.9538	5.4513
Have you heard of the AfCFTA	-0.1009	0.3995	-0.253	.8016	-0.9046	0.7027
digital method used to reach international customers	0.0765	0.1544	0.495	.6226	-0.2341	0.3871

4.5 Discussion of Findings

4.5.1 Factors that Influence SMEs Participation in International Trade in Lusaka Kamwala Trading Center.

The study findings revealed that all SMEs participated in this study were engaged in international trade, either through export or import activities, highlighting the importance of global markets to their business operations. This significant finding suggests that SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center are actively participating in international trade, despite the challenges they may face.

The study noted that majority of these businesses derive a significant proportion of their revenue from international trade, with 66% earning more than half of their revenue from international trade. This finding concurs with the findings of Abdallah et al. (2025), who noted that SMEs in developing countries are increasingly engaging in international trade as a means of expanding their customer base and increasing revenue.

The study noted main factor influencing SMEs' ability to engage in international trade among them is a product quality and standards, cited by 50% of respondents. This is in line with the assertions of Alex and Taonaziso (2021), who emphasized the importance of meeting international quality standards for SMEs to compete in global markets. This finding suggests that SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center recognize the importance of producing high-quality products that meet international standards in order to succeed in global markets.

The chi-square test results indicate that there is no significant association between the type of business and the main factor influencing the ability to engage in international trade, suggesting that the factors influencing international trade engagement are likely to be similar across different types of businesses (Abdallah et al. 2025). This finding is consistent with the idea that SMEs face similar challenges and opportunities in international trade, regardless of their type of business.

In summary, the findings of this study highlight the importance of international trade to SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center and the challenges they face in engaging in global markets. The study underscores the need for SMEs to focus on product quality and standards, understand buyer preferences, and access support programs to enhance their international trade activities.

4.5.2 The Challenges Faced by SMEs in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center when Engaging in International Trade

The study found that SMEs in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center face significant challenges when engaging in international trade. High transportation costs, currency exchange rate risks, and delays at borders/customs are the major challenges affecting these businesses, with 42%, 38%, and 20% of respondents citing these issues, respectively. These findings are consistent with previous studies, which have shown that transportation costs and logistics are major barriers to international trade for SMEs in developing countries (Arvis et al., 2010).

Access to financing is the biggest challenge facing SMEs in international trade, with 44% of respondents citing this issue. This is in line with the findings of previous studies, which have shown that access to finance is a major constraint for SMEs in developing countries (Beck & Demircuc-Kunt, 2006). Customs procedures and competition from large firms are also significant hurdles for SMEs, affecting 30% and 26% of respondents, respectively.

The study's findings also highlight the significant financial requirements for SMEs to engage or expand in international trade. The majority of respondents (84%) estimate needing substantial funding, between ZMW 50,001 and over ZMW 100,000, to expand into international trade. This is consistent with the findings of previous studies, which have shown that SMEs in developing countries face significant financial constraints when attempting to engage in international trade (OECD, 2009).

The regression analysis results indicate that the model is not a good fit for the data, and the independent variables (type of business and years of operation) do not have a statistically significant relationship with the dependent variable (biggest challenge faced by the business in international trade). This suggests that other factors not included in the model are more important in determining the biggest challenge faced by businesses in international trade.

In comparison to other studies, the findings of this study are consistent with the idea that SMEs in developing countries face significant challenges when engaging in international trade. The study's findings highlight the need for policymakers and practitioners to address these challenges and provide support to SMEs in order to enhance their participation in international trade.

4.5.3 Explore the Opportunities Available for SMEs to Enhance their Involvement in Global Markets at Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center.

The findings of this study reveal that SMEs in Lusaka's Kamwala Trading Center are aware of the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) and are leveraging digital methods to reach international customers. The majority of respondents (84%) have heard of AfCFTA, indicating a high level of awareness about this landmark agreement. This is consistent with the findings of previous studies, which have shown that SMEs in developing countries are increasingly aware of the importance of international trade agreements (OECD, 2018).

The study also found that social media is the primary digital method used by SMEs to reach international customers, with 52% of respondents citing this approach. This is consistent with the findings of previous studies, which have shown that social media is an effective tool for SMEs to access global markets (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010).

The top opportunity for enhancing international trade is partnering with foreign buyers/distributors, cited by 38% of respondents. This is consistent with the findings of previous studies, which have shown that partnerships with foreign firms are an effective way for SMEs to access international markets (Hollensen, 2011). The study also found that affordable finance is the most critical form of support required to boost business growth in international trade, with 42% of respondents citing this need. This is consistent with the findings of previous studies, which have shown that access to finance is a major constraint for SMEs in developing countries (Beck & Demircuc-Kunt, 2006).

The regression analysis results indicate that the model is not a good fit for the data, and the independent variables (awareness of AfCFTA and digital method used to reach international customers) do not have a statistically significant relationship with the number of international customers or partners. This suggests that other factors not included in the model are more important in determining the number of international customers or partners.

In comparison to other studies, the findings of this study are consistent with the idea that SMEs in developing countries face significant challenges when engaging in international trade, but also have opportunities to leverage digital methods and partnerships to access global markets.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

In conclusion, the study reveals that SMEs in Kamwala Trading Center are actively engaged in international trade, but face significant challenges such as product quality and standards, understanding buyer preferences, and access to financing. The study also highlights the importance of awareness and utilization of digital methods, such as social media, to reach international customers. Furthermore, partnering with foreign buyers/distributors is identified as a key opportunity for enhancing international trade. The study's findings underscore the need for policymakers and practitioners to address the challenges faced by SMEs and provide support to enhance their participation in international trade.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations are made:

- Capacity Building: Provide training and capacity-building programs for SMEs to enhance their product quality and standards, as well as their understanding of buyer preferences.
- Access to Finance: Improve access to finance for SMEs, including affordable credit and grants, to support their international trade activities.
- Digital Literacy: Enhance digital literacy among SMEs, including the use of social media and e-commerce platforms, to reach international customers.
- Partnerships: Encourage partnerships between SMEs and foreign buyers/distributors to enhance international trade opportunities.
- Awareness and Dissemination: Improve awareness and dissemination of information about support programs and initiatives available to SMEs in international trade.

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